

Role of bridging ligand in tuning metal-metal interaction in mixed valence complexes

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Optical intervalence electron depends both on the nature of the donor/acceptor and on the bridging ligand which joins donor and acceptor sites. The ability to control electronic and magnetic interactions between metal centers with the change in conjugation, conformation and length of BL is of fundamental importance in inorganic and material chemistry. In this article, we review recent reports on the effect of different parameters on intramolecular electron transfer at room temperature of Class II type mixed valence system.

The experimental and theoretical study of intervalence electron transfer between the two metal centers linked by conjugated spacer is a very active research topic. The consequence of this process are of crucial importance in domains such as biology, solid-state chemistry, inorganic reaction mechanisms and finally the emerging field of molecular electronics.

Optical intervalence electron transfer involves transfer of an electron from one nearly localized site to an adjacent one, where donor and acceptor both are metal ions which possess more than one accessible oxidation state. In this article, we review recent reports on the effect of bridging ligand, temperature and pressure on intramolecular electron transfer at room temperature of Class II type mixed valence system. In Marcus theory of electron transfer¹, the energy of absorption maxima ($h\nu_{\max}$) of the inter-valence charge transfer (IVCT) band gives direct information on reorganization energy (χ) and driving force (ΔG^0),

$$E_{OP} = h\nu_{\max} + \Delta G^0 \quad (1)$$

IVCT band also gives a measure of a key electron transfer parameter such as ν_{el} (electron hopping frequency in the intersection region) and H_{AB} (electronic coupling matrix element) (Fig. 1), which can be used to calculate the rate for optical and thermal electron transfer.

However, in the following discussion nuclear tunneling corrections will be neglected; such corrections are not large unless the temperature is low or the activation process involves changes in high frequency modes². In absence of such effects, the first order rate constant for intramolecular electron transfer (k) between donor and acceptor site is given as

$$k_{th} = \kappa_{el} \nu_{el} K_n \quad (2)$$

where κ_{el} is electronic transmission coefficient, ν_{el} , as mentioned earlier, is electron hopping frequency or electronic

nuclear vibration frequency that destroys the activated complex configuration and K_n is nuclear factor,

Fig. 1. Potential energy vs normal mode coordinate (A) for symmetrical electron transfer, $\Delta E = 0$ and (B) for electron transfer in asymmetric mixed-valence complex W_0 is zero order barrier for thermal electron transfer. Other symbols have their usual significance and are mentioned in the text

Electron transfer reaction is adiabatic ($\kappa_{el} \sim 1$) when electronic coupling between the two redox centers and probability of electron transfer in the activated complex are high. For non-adiabatic system, $\kappa_{el} \ll 1$, when electron transfer probability is low. With in Landau-Zener treatment of avoided crossing³, κ_{el} is given by

$$\kappa_{el} = \frac{2[1 - \exp(-\nu_{el}/2\nu_n)]}{[2 - \exp(-\nu_{el}/2\nu_n)]} \quad (3)$$

and

$$\nu_{el} = \frac{2\pi H_{AB}^2}{h(\pi / \chi RT)^{1/2}} \quad (4)$$

where h is the Plank's constant and R the universal gas constant.

Provided the free-energy surface representing the reactants and products are harmonic with identical reduced force

constant, the classical nuclear factor K_n is given by eqs. 5-7, where ΔG^\ddagger is the contribution to the free energy of activation from nuclear reorganization and ΔG^0 the free energy change for electron transfer,

$$K_n = \exp(\Delta G^\ddagger/RT) \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta G^\ddagger = \frac{(\chi + \Delta G^0)^2}{4\chi} \quad (6)$$

where, $\chi = \chi_{in} + \chi_{out}$

χ_{in} is the changes in the intramolecular bond distances and angles, and χ_{out} the changes in the polarization of the surrounding media.

$$k_{th} = \kappa_{el} \nu_{el} \exp(\Delta G^\ddagger/RT) \quad (7)$$

For an optical transmission, $\Delta E = \Delta H = \Delta G$, since there is no change in entropy or volume during a vertical transmission as there is no time for a volume change during vertical transmission which occurs at constant nuclear coordinates⁴. Thus E_{op} is really the vertical difference between the enthalpies (energies) of the ground and excited states,

$$E_{op} = \chi + \Delta E^0 \quad (8)$$

where ΔE is the energy difference between the donor and acceptor sites χ , the reorganization energy, mentioned in eq. 1, can also be evaluated from E_{op} and ΔE , where ΔE can be evaluated from the redox potential of the metal center involved, i.e. donor and acceptor,

$$\Delta E = E_{1/2}^d - E_{1/2}^a \quad (9)$$

Relationship between the coupling elements for thermal and optical electron transfer

Information regarding the magnitude of the electronic coupling element can be obtained from the intensities of the intervalence charge transfer transitions in mixed valence systems. Perturbation theory approach of the Hush model⁵, for the Class II type mixed valence systems, accounts for the degree of electronic coupling between donor and acceptor wave function by using information derived from the IVCT band oscillator strength. Assuming a gaussian band shape, a lower limit for $\Delta\nu_{1/2}$ at room temperature can be obtained from the equation,

$$\Delta\nu_{1/2} = (2304 \nu)^{1/2} \quad (10)$$

where $\Delta\nu_{1/2}$ is the band width (cm^{-1}) at half ϵ_{max} , where ϵ_{max} is molar absorptivity of the IVCT band and ν the frequency of the IVCT transition at ϵ_{max} (cm^{-1}). H_{AB} , the extent of ground state electronic coupling arising for orbital mixing, is given by

$$H_{AB} = [(2.05 \times 10^{-2} r)] (\epsilon_{\text{max}} \Delta\nu_{1/2})^{1/2} \quad (11)$$

where r is the separation between donor-acceptor wave function.

Theoretical value of the ground state delocalization (α^2) and oscillator strength (f) in mixed valence complex can also be obtained using eqs. 12 and 13,

$$\alpha^2 = \frac{4.24 \times 10^{-4} \epsilon_{\text{max}} \Delta\nu_{1/2}}{\nu_{\text{max}} r^2} \quad (12)$$

$$f = 1.085 \times 10^{-5} \nu_{\text{max}} (\alpha r)^2 \quad (13)$$

Further using two stage Hush-Mulliken description for the valence trapped system, it is possible to estimate (eq. 14) the approximate fraction of the charge transferred (F) during intervalence absorption⁶,

$$F = 1 - 2 (H_{AB}/E_{OP}) \quad (14)$$

However, simple approach for calculating the electronic coupling on the basis of Hush model has been questioned in recent times⁷. A more elaborate method for evaluating electronic coupling has been described by Hush *et al*⁸, which is not very straightforward. Moreover, these equations prove to be remarkably successful in providing a basis for understanding optical charge transfer process in a number of weakly coupled, valence localized Class II type chemical systems.

Role of bridging ligand

Bridging ligand (BL) plays a very crucial role in effecting the metal - metal (M-M) interaction in IVCT transition. Pyrazine was the first BL to be used for designed synthesis of mixed valence complexes which had shown IVCT transition⁹. Since then 4,4'-bipy and its derivative, polyenes with varying length and CN^- ion are the most popular spacer groups for linking redox active metal centers for studying the stimulating role of BL in IVCT transitions. For complexes having low-lying π^* BL orbitals, electron transfer between the two metal center through the BL can be shown as

In this case, M-M transition is expected to depend on the energy gap between $d_{\pi}(M_1)$ or $d_{\pi}(M_2)$ and LUMO of BL orbital. Further double coordination of BL lowers $\pi^*(BL)$ orbital, so that each binding site may couple more efficiently with individual metal core. However, this effect is more prominent for the metal ions which can have appreciable

$\pi_d^{\text{metal}} - \pi_p^*$ (BL) overlap, i.e. $M \rightarrow L$ back-bonding effect. However, as the distance between two redox centers increases, i.e. with the increase in the length of the conjugated spacer, the extent of interaction between two metal ions tends to decrease.

The deduced intermetallic coupling are consistent with the theoretical prediction of near exponential bridge-length dependence. Woitellier *et al.*¹⁰ and Reimers and Hush^{11,12} reported the bis(pentaammineruthenium) complexes of α,ω -dipyridyl-*trans*-polyenes ($\text{py}(\text{CH}=\text{CH})_n\text{py}$, where $n = 1-4$) and correlated the electronic coupling parameters derived from IVCT band with the separation distance between the two metal ions (Table 1). The electronic coupling parameters of these complexes decreased only by about 30% when going from $n = 2$ to $n = 4$ as a result of the increase in the distance between the two ions. Slow decrease of the electronic interaction with the increase in the M-M distance has also been predicted by Larson using MO calculations¹³. The theoretical calculation by Reimers and Hush^{11,12} verifies the physical interpretation of the spectra and support the original prediction of a very weak dependence of the coupling on the bridge length. Thus electronic interaction is transmitted well by the conjugated backbone, at least much better than that transmitted across the saturated system like protein.

Table 1. Properties of the intervalence charge transfer band for the polyenes bridged complexes^d

Ligand	K_c	ν_{max} cm^{-1}	$\Delta\nu_{1/2}$ cm^{-1}	ϵ $\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$	r Å	H_{AB} cm^{-1}
$(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Ru-py}(\text{CH}=\text{CH})_n\text{pyRu}(\text{NH}_3)_5^{5+ a,b}$						
$n = 0^a$	23	9200	4800	860	11.2	390
$n = 1^a$	15.4	9900	5300	755	13.4	300
$n = 2$	14.0	8800	3930	1430	15.7	280
$n = 3$	11.9	8410	4810	1250	18.0	260
$n = 4$	10.5	9060	3540	1220	20.3	180
$\text{CpFeCp}-(\text{CH}=\text{CH})_n-\text{CpFeCp}^+$						
$n = 1$		4910	4360	1340	7.03	495
$n = 2$		5500	4340	1570	9.21	430
$n = 3$		6010	800	2100	11.54	390
$n = 4$		6070	3700	1670	13.87	290
$n = 5$		5860	3600	1600	16.29	230
$n = 6$		5565	3600	1600	18.71	195

Bis(pentaammineruthenium) complexes of α,ω -dipyridyl-*trans*-polyenes ($\text{py}(\text{CH}=\text{CH})_n\text{py}$, where $n \geq 1$) may also undergo torsional motion which destroys the planarity of the $\text{C}=\text{C}-\text{C}=\text{C}$ units. These torsions are expected to be smaller in amplitude than the torsions involving the rings. The number of such torsions increases as the chain-length

(n) increases. However, it is difficult to quantify these effects. The effect of torsions involving aromatic rings is demonstrated by Launay and Sauvage (Table 2)¹⁵. Higher interaction and ground state electronic coupling for $[(\text{terpy})\text{Ru}]_2\text{L}_2$ (where L_2 is bisbipybenz) can be explained on the basis of Hückel calculation, which reveals that replacement of N-atom by C-atom on terpy type complexes raises the energy of filled ligand level, i.e. HOMO of BL and thereby increasing the mixing with ligand orbitals and thus the M-M coupling. Representative energy position of ligand L_1 and L_2 and ruthenium $4d$ -orbital is shown in Fig. 2 (diagram is limited to b_{2u} and b_{3u} orbitals only).

Fig. 2

IVCT process for a series of diferrocenyl polyenes of general formula $\text{Fc}-(\text{CH}=\text{CH})_n-\text{Fc}$ with $n = 1-6$ is included in Table 1¹⁶. Well-defined intervalence transitions are observed for these complexes in CH_2Cl_2 upon partial electrolytic oxidation. The corrected spectra of the mixed valence species have been deconvoluted to calculate the desired parameters from the IVCT band. The decay of H_{AB} with distance is close to an exponential law with an exponent 0.087Å^{-1} , smallest attenuation reported so far.

Table 2. Properties of the intervalence charge transfer band for the terpy analog bridged complexes $\{(\text{tpy})\text{Ru}\}_2\text{L}$

L	ν cm^{-1}	$\Delta\nu_{1/2}$ cm^{-1}	H_{AB} cm^{-1}
bisterpy	6329	4008	379
bisbipybenz	4545	2665	1024
1,4-phenyl(bisbipybenz)	10152	7500	226

In our laboratory we have studied the effect of BL on the IVCT band of heterobinuclear complexes, $[(\text{edta})\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}-\text{L}-\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{CN})_5]^{17}$, where $\text{L} = \text{pyrazine}$, $4,4'$ -bipyridyl, $3,3'$ -dimethyl, $4,4'$ -bipyridyl, *trans*-1,2-bis(4-pyridyl)ethylene and 1,3-bis(4-pyridyl)propane (Table 3). These complexes also show IVCT band in the region $900 < \lambda < 1000 \text{ nm}$ and there is a decrease in the electronic interaction with the increase in the metal-metal distance.

Table 3. Properties of the IVCT band containing pyridine and its derivative as bridged ligands

L	r Å	ν_{\max} cm ⁻¹	ϵ_{\max} M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	$\Delta\nu_{1/2}$ cm ⁻¹	α^2	H_{AB} cm ⁻¹
[(<i>edta</i>)Ru ^{III} -L-Fe ^{II} (CN) ₅]						
pyz	5.7	10917	2700	5020	0.01138	1164
4,4'-bipy	11.3	10718	2500	4975	0.0041	683
dimbipy	11.3	10163	2400	4845	0.004	640
etybipy	13.8	10030	2200	4813	0.0026	513
[Ru(NH ₃) ₅ -L-Ru(NH ₃) ₅] ⁵⁺						
pyz ^a	9.13	6060	1550	3900	0.0098	600
dicybenz ^b	11.8	11628	580	5600	-	315
tfdicybenz ^b	11.8	10000	600	5000	-	210
imidazole ^c	-	7273	1000	4300	0.0068	602
[(NH ₃) ₅ Ru-L-Ru(CN) ₅] ⁸						
4cypy	9.13	-	-	-	0.00058	345
[(NH ₃) ₅ Ru-L-Ru(CN) ₅]						
pyz ^d	5.7	6400	-	-	0.0098	600
4cypy ^e	9.13	10173	850	3900	0.0015	410
4-pyincotinamid ^f	-	15504	570	5100	0.00095	480
imidazole ^c	-	10214	962	5000	0.0054	756

^aRef. 18. ^bRef. 19. ^cRef. 20. ^dRef. 21. ^eRef. 22. ^fRef. 23. ^gRef. 18(b).

A related class of bridging ligands has been studied by Ribou *et al.*²⁴. Two new bridging ligands, bis(dipyridyl)furan (BPF) and bis(dipyridyl)thiophene (BPTh) were used for the synthesis of bis(pentaammineruthenium) complexes and their intervalence band electronic coupling parameters were evaluated and compared with that for related polyene bridged¹⁰⁻¹² complexes. The difference in coupling parameters between polyenes and dipyridylheterocycles bridged complexes could be due to the more rigid conformations of the latter ligands. The weak IVCT (Table 4) observed in these complexes may be due to the increase in the bridging ligand energy level owing to the lone-pair of electron on the hetero atom.

Table 4. Properties of the IVCT band for the BPF and BPTh bridged complexes

L	K_c	[Ru(NH ₃) ₅ -L-Ru(NH ₃) ₅] ⁵⁺				
		ν_{\max} cm ⁻¹	$\Delta\nu_{1/2}$ cm ⁻¹	ϵ M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	r Å	H_{AB} cm ⁻¹
BPF	50	10080	5515	520	13.7	254
BPTh	14	10151	6610	410	14.5	240

IVCT parameters for strongly coupled binuclear complexes of general formula {Ru(NH₃)₅}₂L are presented in Table 5²⁵. It is evident that the M-M coupling increases as the energy of the π -HOMO for the ligand is raised by removing electron-withdrawing substituents or by introducing electron-donating substituents on the phenyl ring.

Table 5. Properties of the IVCT band for the dicyano bridged complexes

L	K_c	$\nu, \Delta\nu$ cm ⁻¹	$\times 10^4 \epsilon_{\max}$ M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	f
Me ₂ dicyd ²⁻	1.3×10 ⁷	7970; 1760	1.18	0.096
dicyd ²⁻	9.3×10 ⁶	7580; 1940	1.85	0.16
Cl ₂ dicyd ²⁻	3.5×10 ⁵	6910; 2440	2.8	0.31

It is worth mentioning here that change in ancillary ligand also affects the energy for the IVCT transition between the same set of metal core and bridging ligand (Table 6)²⁵. Replacement of the amine ligand by pyridine/2,2'-bipy/2,2',2''-terpyridyl ligand lowers the energy of the π_d^{metal} and thereby enhances the M-M coupling. Thus M-M coupling may be maximized by minimizing the energy gap between the metal and ligand orbitals. This is demonstrated nicely by another series of tailor-made trinuclear complexes of general formula Fc-L-Fc, where Fc is ferrocenyl unit and L

Complex 1

Complex 2: L=CO; 3: L=C₆H₅N; 3: L=P(OMe)₃

Fig. 3

Table 6. Effect of ancillary ligands on IVCT parameters*

Ligand				
	$K_c(f)$	$K_c(f)$	$K_c(f)$	$K_c(f)$
Me ₂ dicyd ²⁻	5.6×10^5 (0.22)	5.2×10^6 (0.19)	1.3×10^7 (0.096)	–
dicyd ²⁻	6.9×10^4 (0.25)	1.2×10^6 (0.23)	9.3×10^6 (0.16)	2.7×10^7 (0.046)
Cl ₂ dicyd ²⁻	3.9×10^3 (0.21)	2.7×10^4 (0.26)	2.5×10^5 (0.31)	–
Cl ₄ dicyd ²⁻	3.3×10^2 (0.14)	7.2×10^2 (0.26)	–	–

* K_c is comproportion constant and f is oscillator strength.

Table 7. Effect of substituents (electron-donating and -withdrawing) on the bridging ligand on IVCT parameters

Complex ^a no.	ν_{\max} cm ⁻¹	ϵ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	$\Delta\nu_{1/2}$ cm ⁻¹	α^2
1	2095	6700	3300	0.047
	2285	2900	700	–
2	1245	2410	3500	0.012
	2285	410	540	–
3	1555	3200	2900	0.016
	2265	1100	510	–
4	1535	2900	3100	0.015
	2250	1100	530	–

^aStructure of the complexes 1, 2, 3 and 4 are shown in Fig. 3.

is ruthenium biacetylene bridge (Fig. 3)²⁶ (Table 6). Ruthenium biacetylene bridge in these complexes allows electronic interaction between two terminal ferrocene groups. The interaction is enhanced when ancillary ligands on ruthenium center are electron-donor and lessened when the ligands are electron-acceptor.

Now according to Hush model, the energy $E_{op} = h\nu \geq 4E_{th}$, where E_{op} is the summation of E_{FC} (Frank-Condon energy for a symmetrical one electron transfer) and the E_0 (zero point energy between the two asymmetric vibronic states),

$$E_{op} = E_{FC} + E_0$$

Thus the Hush model predicts that the IVCT band for an asymmetric system will be blue-shifted relative to symmetrical ones. For an unsymmetrically substituted mixed valence compound, electron transfer will result in the formation of an energetically unfavorable valence isomer. This is demonstrated nicely by Dong *et al.*²⁷ (Table 8). The observed blue-shift in IVCT band correlates nicely with the magnitude of the zero point energy difference.

Cyano-bridged mixed valence complexes

The study of intramolecular electron transfer using

Table 8. Effect of asymmetry on IVCT parameters

Complex	ν_{\max} cm ⁻¹	ϵ mol ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	$\Delta\nu_{1/2}$ cm ⁻¹
	4805	1157	3394
	4776	1218	3342
	4458	1305	3434

binuclear transition metal mixed valence complexes has seen much progress recently²⁸ as cyanide provides a substantial amount of metal-metal electronic coupling due to the short distance between the two metal ions. We have synthesised new cyano-bridged complexes incorporating Ru^{III} and Fe^{II} and studied their physicochemical and spectral properties,

where $M_1 = \text{Ru}$ and $M_2 = \text{Fe}$ or Ru . IVCT parameters of some of the complexes are presented in Table 9.

For all binuclear complexes incorporating Ru^{III} and Fe^{II} or Ru^{II} (Table 9), E_{op} and ΔE (separation of the $E_{1/2}$ values for couples $M_1^{\text{III/II}}$ and $M_2^{\text{III/II}}$) change with the change in temperature. The temperature dependence term ($d\Delta E/dT$) of the

Table 9. Properties of intervalence charge transfer band for the cyano-bridged complexes

Compd.	ν_{\max} cm ⁻¹	ϵ_{\max} cm ⁻¹	$\Delta\nu_{1/2}$ cm ⁻¹	α^2	H_{AB} cm ⁻¹
[(edta)Ru ^{III} (μ -NC)Fe ^{II} (CN) ₅] ⁵⁻ ^a	10638	2900	5802	0.0118	1580
[(edta)Ru ^{III} (μ -NC)Ru ^{II} (CN) ₅] ⁵⁻ ^b	14560	2700	5312	0.0197	1490
[(hedtra)Ru ^{III} (μ -NC)Fe ^{II} (CN) ₅] ^{-c}	10360	2650	5600	0.011	1400
[(NH ₃) ₅ Ru ^{III} (μ -NC)Ru ^{II} (CN) ₅] ^{-d}	14793	2800	5050	0.019	2020
[(NH ₃) ₅ Ru ^{III} (μ -NC)Fe ^{II} (CN) ₅] ^{-e}	10630	2300	6582	0.022	1500
K ₂ [dmbRe(CO) ₃ (μ -NC)Fe ^{II} (CN) ₅] ^f	21120	165	8740	0.033	760
K[dmbRe(CO) ₃ (μ -NC) ₂ Fe ^{II} (CN) ₄] ₂ ^g	18420	390	7510	0.034	643
[dmbRe(CO) ₃ (μ -NC) ₃ Fe ^{II} (CN) ₄] ₃ ^f	17270	470	6150	0.029	505
[(NH ₃) ₅ Ru ^{III} (μ -NC)Ru ^{II} (cp)(PPh ₃) ₂] ^{-g}	14900	3210	5000	0.0169	1940
[(NH ₃) ₅ Os ^{III} (μ -NC)Ru ^{II} (cp)(PPh ₃) ₂] ^{-g}	18345	2474	6590	0.0139	2165
	20615	2445			

^aRef. 29. ^bRef. 30. ^cRef. 31. ^dRef. 32. ^eRef. 33. ^fRef. 34. ^gRef. 35.

Table 10. Effect of temperature on ΔE and E_{op} of some μ -CN complexes

Compd.	E_{op} cm ⁻¹	dE_{op}/dT cm ⁻¹ deg ⁻¹	Charge type on Ru fragments	Charge type on Fe/Ru fragments	$d\Delta E/dT$ cm ⁻¹ deg ⁻¹
[(edta)Ru ^{III} (μ -NC)Fe ^{II} (CN) ₅] ⁵⁻	10638	-5	-1/-2	-3/-4	-6
[(edta)Ru ^{III} (μ -NC)Ru ^{II} (CN) ₅] ⁵⁻	14560	-4	-1/-2	-3/-4	-3.45
(hedtra)Ru ^{III} (μ -NC)Fe ^{II} (CN) ₅] ⁴⁻	10360	-5	-0/-1	-3/-4	-6.2
[(NH ₃) ₅ Ru ^{III} (μ -NC)Ru ^{II} (CN) ₅] ⁻	14793	-14.5	+3/+2	-3/-4	-
[(NH ₃) ₅ Ru ^{III} (μ -NC)Fe ^{II} (CN) ₅] ⁻	10630	13.4	+3/+2	-3/-4	-9.2

thermal effect can be expressed as

where E_f is the formal potential for M(III)/M(II) electrochemical process, and

$$\Delta S_{rc} = \Delta S_{rc}^{\circ}(M_1) - \Delta S_{rc}^{\circ}(M_2)$$

$$= dE_f(M_1)/dT - dE_f(M_2)/dT = \Delta E/dT.$$

Fig. 4. dE_{op}/dT and $d\Delta E/dT$ plots for [(edta)Ru^{III}(μ -NC)Ru^{II}(CN)₅]⁵⁻.

A representative plot of E_{op}/dT and $\Delta E/dT$ for complex [(edta)Ru^{III}(μ -NC)Ru^{II}(CN)₅]⁵⁻ is shown in Fig. 4.

The difference between $\Delta E/dT$ and E_{op}/dT (Table 10) reveals a measure of the effect of other temperature-dependent component χ , the reorganization parameter. χ seems to be very sensitive to the cationic environment of M₁ and/or M₂. The difference between $\Delta E/dT$ and E_{op}/dT (Table 8) is more significant for complex [(NH₃)₅Ru^{III}(μ -NC)Fe^{II}(CN)₅]⁻ than for [(edta)Ru^{III}(μ -NC)Fe^{II}(CN)₅]⁵⁻ or (hedtra)Ru^{III}(μ -NC)Fe^{II}(CN)₅]⁻ as the effective charge type for (NH₃)₅Ru core is 3+, whereas that for (edta)Ru or (hedtra)Ru core is 0/+1 respectively. This presumption is further reinforced by the report of Dong and Hupp³⁷. The values for dE_{op}/dT (-18 cm⁻¹ deg⁻¹) and $d\Delta E/dT$ (-8 cm⁻¹ deg⁻¹) are found to differ by a factor more than two for a complex [(2,2'-bipy)₂CiRu(py_z)Ru(NH₃)₅]⁴⁺, in which the effective charge on each metal core is +2.

Effect of pressure

There are only a few reports describing the effect of pressure on IVCT band in mixed valence complexes. Hammarck *et al.* first reported³⁸ that there was no significant shift in

Ligand structure with the abbreviated form used in the text :

energy in the IVCT band for ferrocenium binuclear and for the complex $[(2,2'\text{-bipy})_2\text{ClRu}(\text{pyz})\text{ClRu}(2,2'\text{-bipy})_2]^{3+}$. Later the same group reported³⁹ the effect of pressure on Creutz-Taube ion and a positive shift of $\sim 35\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in IVCT band with the increase in pressure. Lewis *et al.*⁴¹ studied pressure effect on weakly coupled mixed valence complex, (μ -2,6-dithiaspiro[3,3]heptane)decaamminediruthenium(II,III) in D_2O and observed a shift of more than 200 cm^{-1} and a small increase in oscillator strength over a pressure range of 1500 bars. In general, the $\Delta\nu_{1/2}$ of the IVCT bands remain unaltered while the maximum absorbance of the complex increases by *ca* 5–7% and E_{op} shift by $100\text{--}250\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with the change in pressure. Pressure effect on IVCT band maxima has been explained on the basis of solvent reorganization and the H-bonding interaction between the solvent and the coordinated ligands in the binuclear complexes. This hypothesis is further consolidated by a recent study⁴² on the complexes $[(\text{edta})\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}(\mu\text{-NC})\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{CN})_5]^{5-}$ and $[(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}(\mu\text{-NC})\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}(\text{CN})_5]^-$.

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